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Effect of Pyrosulphate Fusion on the Oxidation State of Platinum Group Metals†

C. S. DORAI, P. UMAPATHY* and S. BADRINARAYANAN

National Chemical Laboratory, Poona-411 008

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revised 20 August 1990, accepted 10 October 1990

TRACE amounts of rhodium are generally determined by spectrophotometric methods using stannous chloride¹ or bromide² or by d.c. polarography³ by the reduction of Rh^{III}-pyridine complex. Standard rhodium solutions are prepared⁴ by fusing rhodium metal with potassium pyrosulphate. However, it is observed that during fusion of Rh⁰ or RhCl₃.xH₂O with K₂S₂O₇, rhodium is oxidised to quinequivalent state. Pyrosulphate-induced oxidation of rhodium or other platinum group metals during fusion has not been reported so far. While the determination of traces of rhodium by spectrophotometric methods after fusion with K₂S₂O₇ may give accurate results, its estimation by differential pulse polarography method leads to serious errors because of the change in the oxidation state of the metal. Experimental evidence for the oxidation of rhodium (or other platinum group) metal(s) or metal salts during fusion with K₂S₂O₇-polarographic, coulometric and ESCA, is presented here.

Experimental

The method followed to estimate traces of rhodium by differential pulse polarography was essentially the same as described by Willis³ for rhodium estimation by d.c. polarography. A 100 ppm rhodium standard solution was prepared by fusing 10 mg of finely divided rhodium metal (99.99% purity, Johnson Matthey) with 1 or 2 g of potassium pyrosulphate in a silica crucible until it was brought into solution. The melt was dissolved in 1 N sulphuric acid and diluted to 100 ml with the same acid. Aliquots from this stock solution in 1M

pyridine and 1M KCl were polarogrammed after purging the solution with oxygen-free nitrogen using a PAR 174A polarographic analyser over the range 0 to -1.5 V (vs Ag/AgCl). The expected well-defined peak at -0.414 V was however not observed. The same aliquots, however, after fuming with concentrated HCl several times and complexed with 1M pyridine containing 1M KCl, gave well-defined differential pulse polarographic peak at -0.46 V (vs Ag/AgCl). The working range was found to be 1-10 ppm (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DIFFERENTIAL PULSE POLAROGRAPHY OF Rh-PYRIDINE COMPLEX IN 1M KCl

Peak potentials (E_p) = -0.46 V (vs Ag/AgCl), Scan rate = 2 mV s⁻¹, modulation amplitude 50 mV and scan range 0 to -1.5 V.

Conc. of Rh ppm	i_p (μ A)	
	A	B
1.00	0.98	1.97
2.00	1.98	3.93
3.00	2.96	5.89
4.00	3.90	7.79
5.00	4.94	9.86
6.00	5.88	11.80
7.00	6.85	13.68
8.00	7.88	15.74
9.00	8.83	17.70
10.00	9.82	19.66

A = RhCl₃.xH₂O unfused and unfumed. B = Rh metal or RhCl₃.xH₂O fused and fumed.

The anionic rhodium(v) complex as its tetrabutylammonium salt (C₄H₉)₄N[RhI₆] was isolated by mixing aqueous solutions of the fused product (pale pink colour) and tetrabutylammonium iodide (Found: C, 17.63; H, 4.07; N, 1.76; Rh, 10.46. Calcd. for C₁₆H₃₆NRhI₆: C, 17.35; H, 3.28; N, 1.27; Rh, 9.3%). Binding energy of Rh 3d_{5/2}, 313.8 eV, 313.4 eV. Other platinum group metal chlorides, K₂PtCl₄, K₂PdCl₄, RuCl₃ and IrCl₃.xH₂O were fused with K₂S₂O₇ and treated similarly. The binding energies (in eV) of the metals in the products (Pt 4f_{7/2}, 75.4; Pd 3d_{5/2}, 340.0; 339.46; Ir 4f_{7/2}, 64.16; Ru 3d_{5/2}, 281.9) confirm that these metals undergo oxidation to higher valent state during fusion with K₂S₂O₇-Pt^{II} and Pd^{II} to Pt^{IV} and Pd^{IV}, Ru^{III} and Ir^{III} to possibly Ru^V and Ir^V.

Results and Discussion

The differential pulse polarogram peak heights of rhodium solutions (same concentrations prepared from RhCl₃.xH₂O and analysed spectrophotometrically and by AAS) were exactly half the heights of the standards prepared via fusing rhodium metal with K₂S₂O₇ and later fumed with concentrated HCl. In other words, the peak heights of solutions of rhodium metal fused with K₂S₂O₇ and later fumed with concentrated HCl and the pure RhCl₃.xH₂O solution in 1 M pyridine and KCl were in the ratio 2 : 1. Furthermore, the peak heights of the solutions (same concentration) of RhCl₃.xH₂O

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heated with $K_2S_2O_7$ and fumed with concentrated HCl and complexed with pyridine containing 1 M KCl and $RhCl_3 \cdot xH_2O$, not fused are again in the ratio 2 : 1. Obviously rhodium metal or its hydrated chloride salt when fused with $K_2S_2O_7$ is oxidised to an higher-valent state. The fact that Rh^0/Rh^{III} fused with $K_2S_2O_7$ and fumed with concentrated HCl gave two times the peak height as compared to unfused Rh^{III} solutions, suggests a 4-electron reduction process involving the change from Rh^V to Rh^I . Coulometric analysis of the rhodium solutions at constant potential (-0.55 V) under conditions identical to that of polarography using a PAR 173/179 digital coulometer, is compatible with this finding in that the total number of coulombs obtained from 10 mg of rhodium, i.e. 18.50, in fused Rh^0/Rh^{III} -pyridine complex solution is nearly twice that of the unfused Rh^{III} -pyridine complex solution, i.e. 9.28. It is evident that the number of electrons involved in polarography and in coulometry for the fused Rh is twice that of the unfused rhodium. It is well known⁵ that the reduction of rhodium(III)-pyridine complex involves a two-electron process. Evidently pyrosulphate fusion of Rh^0 or $RhCl_3 \cdot xH_2O$ results in the oxidation to the pentavalent state.

The ESCA binding energies of the metals (given in the experimental section) confirm that the platinum group metals undergo oxidation to higher valent state during fusion with $K_2S_2O_7$. It is known that pyrosulphates on stronger heating decompose to SO_3 and sulphates. Many sulphates begin to decompose at red heat forming metallic oxide or the metal and SO_3 or its decomposition products SO_2 and oxygen, which may be responsible for the oxidation. Formation of the latter is increasingly favoured, the higher the decomposition temperature⁶. In the pyrosulphate fusion, possibly Pt-metal group sulphites, $K[Rh(SO_3)_3]$ are initially formed (qualitatively identified by the green colouration produced when the filter paper moistened with acidified potassium dichromate solution was exposed) and change to $K[RhCl_6]$ on fuming with concentrated HCl.

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Kinetics of Cerium(IV) Oxidation of Salicylidene Aminophenols in Acidic Medium

BALESHWAR SINGH*, V. PAL, N. SINGH

and

B. D. KANSAL

Hindu College, Moradabad-244 221

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accepted 21 November 1990

THERE are many examples in literature which show that cerium(IV) has been used in oxidative determination in a large number of inorganic and organic compounds, e.g. oxidation of ethanol¹, oxidation of *meso*-2,3-butanediol in nitric acid², oxidation of mandelic, *dl*-malic and lactic acid³, and oxidation of citric and tartaric acid and some sugar such as glucose, fructose and arabinose⁴. But the kinetic study of oxidation of Schiff base, e.g. salicylidene *o*-aminophenol and salicylidene *m*-aminophenol by cerium(IV) in acidic medium has not been observed so far.

Experimental

The kinetic run was initiated by adding a temperature equilibrated solution of Schiff base (maintained at 40°) to the required amounts of sulphuric acid and cerium(IV) sulphate solution in double-distilled water. The course of reaction was followed by removing aliquot (5 ml) at different time intervals and determining the unreacted cerium(IV) by ferrous ammonium sulphate solution using ferroin as an indicator.

To know the stoichiometry of the reactions between these two Schiff bases with cerium(IV) sulphate separately, the method was adopted as described in the literature⁵. The equivalent of cerium(IV) used per mole of salicylidene *o*-aminophenol and salicylidene *m*-aminophenol was found to be eight at 40°.

Results and Discussion

Effect of concentration of reactants on reaction rate: The variation in the concentration of Ce^{IV} showed the first order reaction. Straight lines were obtained by plotting $\log [Ce^{IV}]$ vs time separately for each Schiff base and pseudo-first order rate constants (k) were calculated from the slopes of these lines; k value was directly proportional to the concentration of Schiff base. This fact is confirmed by plotting $1/k$ vs $1/[Schiff\ base]$. The plots were straight lines which do not pass through origin but leave an intercept on $1/k$ axis. These facts show complex formation between Ce^{IV} and salicylidene *o*-aminophenol, Ce^{IV} and salicylidene *m*-aminophenol separately, which decompose to product in the rate-determining step. The reaction velocity decreases as the concentration of sulphuric acid increases.